

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP1 – Advancing Instruct through Instruct-ULTRA

Lead Beneficiary: P1 - Instruct

Co-leaders: P2 – UOXF

Deliverable D1.2 Training programme for core facility and Instruct Centre staff

Contractual delivery date: 31/12/2019

Actual delivery date: 28/02/2020

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Executive Summary

Instruct-ULTRA has a strong training mandate, to set up a training programme for core facility and centre staff. The training programme began in May 2017 with the first Instruct Best Practices in CryoEM workshop hosted in Harwell, UK, and continues with a full set of training courses right through to November 2020, with the Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM in Iguazu, Brazil. The training programme covers many topics: Access Management, Quality Management, General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), Best practice in CryoEM, Hydrogen Deuterium Exchange (HDX), International Training Courses and Staff Exchange. Staff from many of the Instruct-ULTRA partner organisations have been called upon to teach as part of the wide-ranging training programme.

Introduction

Staff training is an important activity in any organisation, as the enhanced knowledge, skill and capability of employees can improve productivity and the quality of services. Such training may be offered on a number of grounds, including:

- For new staff who join Instruct, in order to familiarise them with the aims and objectives of the RI; aspects of administration and management; and practical aspects of service delivery
- For existing staff, to refresh or enhance their knowledge and skills, and to share best practice
- To disseminate and demonstrate new technology and methods

In its role of advancing Instruct-ERIC, the ULTRA project has delivered a variety of activities to train core facility staff - particularly those providing access and training for Instruct. In part, such training has focussed on coaching staff in the administrative processes that are required to manage Instruct services, with the aim of standardising and refining processes across all facilities. As the administrative processes continues to evolve, additional guidance will be provided through remote training, short on-line tutorials and workshops. In addition, training in specific structural biology methods has been provided in order to promote new technologies, and to facilitate an exchange of information and optimisation of appropriate quality standards in established methods. A particular focus on quality management and the development of guidelines has sought to standardise and improve delivery of Instruct services. Finally, as a practical outcome of Deliverable 1.4: the 'Dissemination outreach and exploitation plan', ULTRA has plans to deliver training for communications, with the goal of developing and harmonising Instruct communications, and increasing engagement from staff and scientists at the Instruct Centres.

A summary of the topics covered within the Instruct-ULTRA Training Programme is therefore:

1. Access Management: ARIA
2. Quality Management
3. GDPR
4. Communications
5. Best Practice in CryoEM
6. HDX
7. International Training Courses
8. Staff Exchange

In the following report, each type of training course is listed numerically, with information about individual courses and workshops detailed. Some courses have already taken place during RP1 and RP2, other courses are scheduled for RP3.

1. Access Management: ARIA

ARIA is a collection of cloud services provided by Instruct to research infrastructures, facilities and user communities in structural biology and related fields. ARIA hosts a number of tools targeted at the different stages of scientific workflows, with the original product built to deliver access proposal management for research infrastructures. Since its launch, ARIA has been expanded to support and integrate facility management with a visit management workflow and machine booking calendar. Additionally, there are a suite of tools for managing an online website, with support for news, events, jobs, forums and custom page editors.

1.1 Help guides

To assist facility managers in using ARIA, Instruct Hub staff have produced a set of help guides, available on the Instruct website <https://instruct-eric.eu/help/collections>. Help guides are the first line of training to which facility managers are directed when introduced to ARIA and guides are available as the initial source of support when a question arises. In addition, a series of documents is being prepared for new facility managers to provide a deeper understanding of ARIA's systems for managing access.

1.2 ARIA launch event 2017

In July 2017, the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) hosted the ARIA launch event, which was sponsored by Instruct-ULTRA. All Instruct Centre staff and facility managers were invited to the launch event, which showcased new features in ARIA and delivered training to make the best use of the software. Refer to Appendix 1 for the agenda.

1.3 ARIA workshop at Managers Meeting 2018

In February 2018, a follow-up workshop was hosted at the NKI in the Netherlands, with participation from all Instruct Centres, as well as other research infrastructures using ARIA. The workshop was delivered by Instruct Hub staff, who provided hands on-training in the use of ARIA: each participant was asked to bring a laptop in order that they could try out the new features demonstrated during the workshop, with Instruct staff available for guidance. The workshop was a great success, receiving good feedback from participants. Refer to Appendix 2 for the agenda.

All the resources from the workshop, including PowerPoints and worksheets, are available on the Instruct-ERIC website: <https://instruct-eric.eu/instruct-ultra-inext-aria-workshop>.

1.4 ARIA workshop at Managers Meeting 2020

In RP3, a final ARIA workshop will take place at NKI in the Netherlands. The workshop on 24 February 2020, which will be co-sponsored by CORBEL¹, will include training in new features of ARIA, followed by an ARIA user group meeting where key users have been invited to share feedback on new developments and make requests for further development. Refer to Appendix 3 for more information.

¹ <https://www.CORBEL-project.eu/home.html>

1.5 ARIA webinars

In partnership with the CORBEL project, a series of three webinars provided effective training in the use of ARIA directly to facility managers at Instruct and other research infrastructures using ARIA. These workshops were live streamed so that participants could ask questions directly to the training staff, and recordings of the webinars were uploaded to the Instruct website as a resource for future users. The three ARIA webinars were:

16 January 2018: Powering your access management from the cloud

8 May 2018: ARIA training for reviewers

9 May 2018: ARIA training for service providers

Fig 1. Screen shot of webinar for ARIA workshop. Webinar available at <https://instruct-eric.eu/webinars/aria-powering-your-access-management-from-the-cloud>

2. Quality Management

As noted in the Instruct-ULTRA Technical Annex, quality management (QM) was identified as a key area of training for Instruct-ERIC Centre staff. Instruct-ULTRA had the opportunity to sponsor a master's student in quality management from the Université Claude Bernard, Lyon, France, who performed an assessment of QM across Instruct Centres. The master's project fed into a report on quality management at Instruct Centre FR2, and subsequently two training activities at consecutive Instruct Managers Meetings in 2019 and upcoming in 2020. In parallel, a joint open call with ARBRE-MOBIEU², resulted in Instruct-ULTRA co-funding two workshops in quality management. Following the success of the joint Instruct-ARBRE-MOBIEU training, the QM course will be offered again during RP3.

² ARBRE-MOBIEU: a network to ally and synergize spectroscopic, hydrodynamic, real-time microfluidic, thermodynamic and single-molecule approaches across Europe. Website: <https://arbre-mobieu.eu>

2.1 Quality Management Research Project

Through the support of Instruct-ULTRA, Elodie Caremoli (Trainee Quality Engineer) and Auriane Denis-Meyere (CEA Quality Engineer) undertook an assessment to establish the level of Quality Management (formal or informal) in place across the Instruct-ERIC infrastructure. The aim was to understand the current level of implementation and establish a baseline against which progress could be measured in the future. The study, which was based on the requirements of ISO 9001:2015 for a Quality Management System (QMS), began with a five-section questionnaire on the organisation of QM at the Instruct Centres, including:

1. Description of the service activity, from user requests, to reports and results
2. About platform use and user approach for the service activity
3. The general organisation of activities in the laboratories of the centres
4. Questions related to the management commitment (leadership) in the centres in aspects of quality
5. Some standard quality tools to better understand quality management in the centres

Semi-quantitative data was extracted from the responses of the Centre managers and combined to generate global data for the infrastructure. The report, including an action plan to improve QM at the Instruct Centres is provided in Appendix 4.

2.2 QM Training at the Managers Meeting, May 2019

At the Managers Meeting in 2019, Auriane Denis-Meyere (P2 - CNRS) gave a presentation on 'Quality assurance at research infrastructure facilities', which was followed by small group discussions to share thoughts on 'best practices for quality management in the delivery of access to research infrastructures', led by Darren Hart (P2 - CNRS).

2.3 QM Training at the Managers Meeting, February 2020

Following on from the Managers Meeting in 2019, Darren Hart and Auriane Denis-Meyere (Instruct Centre FR2) presented their report on 'Quality management at Instruct-ERIC Centres' at Instruct-ERIC Managers Meeting in Amsterdam, 24 February 2020. The facility managers were given a good explanation of why Quality Management (QM) is important and steps they could take to implement QM. An interesting discussion ensued as facility managers considered the various implications.

Fig 2. Darren Hart presenting QM training at the Instruct-ERIC Managers Meeting, 24 February 2020

2.4 Quality Management for Sample Preparation

To address Quality Control, Instruct-ULTRA partnered with the ARBRE-MOBIEU project³ to host a training workshop. An open call⁴ was launched in January 2019 for workshop proposals to address quality management relevant for a variety of structural biology techniques. During peer review, it became clear that two strong courses were proposed, and with a little further investment by both Instruct-ERIC and Arbre-Mobieu, the two courses could be sponsored:

a) Joint Instruct-ARBRE MOBIEU Workshop: The Quality Control Training School

The Quality Control Training School⁵, hosted at the Pasteur Institute in Paris France 14-18 October 2018, was designed for structural biologists wanting to improve their skills in sample analysis and optimisation for structural techniques, in particular cryo-EM. The course covered different biochemical and biophysical techniques (including chromatography, dynamic and static light scattering, viscometry, circular dichroism, mass spectrometry, and differential scanning fluorimetry) and provided hands-on training in basic quality control of protein, as well as buffer and storage optimisation. Trainees were able to bring their own samples for use during the practical sessions. Ultimately, attendees were provided with the knowledge and skills to apply the aforementioned measurements at their own institution.

b) Joint Instruct-ARBRE MOBIEU Workshop: Analysis and optimisation of sample quality for cryo-electron microscopy and other structural techniques

The joint Instruct-ARBRE MOBIEU Workshop: Analysis and optimisation of sample quality for cryo-electron microscopy and other structural techniques workshop⁶ will take place from 11-14 February 2020 at CEITEC (Instruct Centre CZ, P4-MU). As in 2019, the workshop will target structural biologists wanting to improve their skills in sample analysis and optimisation for structural techniques, in particular cryo-EM. Training will include theory and hands-on activities, with a focus on the importance to provide basic protein quality control as well as buffer and storage optimization using quick and relatively cheap techniques to save cryo-EM time.

3. Training in General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR)

In light of the new GDPR regulations coming into legal force in May 2017, a training module was developed by Naomi Gray (P2-UOXF) and Natalie Haley (P1-INST) at the Instruct Hub to equip Hub and Centre staff to meet GDPR requirements. This training was designed to be interactive and included a set of engaging activities. The training offered to Hub staff in December 2017 was filmed in order that it could be made into a standalone module for use at the Instruct Centres. A short assessment will be developed to accompany the course, with a certificate of achievement to be provided following satisfactory completion.

³ Association of Resources for Biophysical Research in Europe <https://arbre-mobieu.eu>

⁴ <https://arbre-mobieu.eu/instruct-eric-arbre-mobieu-joint-training-course/>

⁵ <https://instruct-eric.eu/events/joint-instruct-arbre-mobieu-workshop-the-quality-control-training-school/>

⁶ <https://instruct-eric.eu/events/joint-instruct-arbre-mobieu-workshop-analysis-and-optimisation-of-sample-quality-for-cryo-electron-m.>

4. Training in Communications

Instruct-ERIC's internal and external communications have been identified as an important focus of Instruct-ULTRA's efforts (Deliverable 1.4). In the last few years, communication methods have advanced rapidly, requiring adoption of new channels (eg social media) and new points of access (eg websites compatible with mobile devices). During RP2, Naomi Gray and Stephanie Chapman have developed the Instruct-ERIC communications policy, strategy and guidelines. Into RP3, training will be provided to the wider infrastructure through meetings, webinars and best practice guides, culminating in a workshop at the Instruct-ULTRA General Assembly in September 2020.

4.1 Communications Mini Workshop at the Instruct-ERIC Managers Meeting 2020

As part of the Instruct-ERIC Managers in February 2020, Instruct-ULTRA will be hosting a mini communications workshop to demonstrate the importance of communication activities across the RI, and to encourage facility managers, staff and scientists to get involved. The interactive workshop will include an overview of Instruct communications, advice for conference presentation and exhibition, a guide to use of Twitter, advice and best practice for websites, and a discussion on internal communications. Attendees will be encouraged to make a communications plan for their facility.

Fig 3. Stephanie Chapman presenting the Communications Mini Workshop in Amsterdam, 24 February 2020

4.2 Communication webinars

In RP3, Instruct-ULTRA will host a series of webinars for Instruct facility staff on various topics relating to communication. Predominantly, the webinars will focus on different communication methods in turn (eg presentation, websites, print, social media), offering guidance and support as well as a forum for staff to ask specific questions relating to communications.

4.3 Communications Mini Workshop September 2020

During the final Instruct-ULTRA General Assembly 22-23 September, part of the agenda will include a mini communications workshop. Building on the training given at the Managers Meeting in February, participants will be given the opportunity to learn more about particular

communications channels, discuss materials that they have been working on, and finalise the communications plan for their centres and countries.

5. Instruct workshop on best practices in CryoEM

An important area highlighted in the Instruct-ULTRA Technical Annex is training facility managers in best practices. Cryo Electron Microscopy (CryoEM) is a relatively recent technology, where there is much to be gained from sharing experience.

The Instruct Workshop for Best Practice in CryoEM was established as a forum for the exchange of knowledge and experience between EM facility scientists, managers and computational experts in academia and industry. The aim is to sharing of best practice in the delivery of cryoEM services and help to identify common issues and solutions in service provision. A secondary purpose is to encourage interaction between scientists and instrument manufacturers, in order to direct developments in training and technology for cryoEM. Instruct-ULTRA sponsored the first Best Practices in CryoEM workshop in May 2017. The success of this event led to a second and subsequent third course in Leiden 2018 and Strasbourg 2019, and plans are underway for a course at the Astbury Biostructure Laboratory at the University of Leeds (Instruct Centre UK) in 2020.

5.1 First Instruct Best Practices in CryoEM 2017

The first Instruct workshop on Cryo-EM best practices took place in Harwell, UK, 9-10 May 2017. There were 29 participants, including 6 from industry. Organised by Ray Owens and Jose-Maria Carazo, the workshop identified. Identifying common issues and solutions, established best practices, and engaged with instrument manufacturers.

5.2 Second Instruct Best Practices in CryoEM 2018

The second Instruct Best Practices in CryoEM workshop was hosted at NeCEN (Instruct-NL Centre P13) 15-16 October 2018. Presentations were made by facility managers of large cryoEM facilities and focus given towards operations, remote control, efficient usage of the machines and live processing, followed by round tables discussions. On the second day, a tour of Thermo Fisher Nanoport and Factory in Eindhoven was organised, where Krios microscopes are assembled. All the talks were filmed so that they could be released online as podcasts⁷, which have proved very popular, some talks have had over 250 in the first year after publishing.

An international dimension was added to the Leiden workshop, as Dr Rodrigo Portugal, the head of new cryo-EM facility at LNNano/CNPEM in Campinas, Brazil, was invited to attend the workshop and give a presentation. This provided a valuable opportunity to exchange experience across continents and learn about the plans for cryo-EM at LNNano.

5.3 Third Instruct Best Practices in CryoEM 2019

On 19 November 2019, scientists from facilities across the world gathered at the IGBMC in Strasbourg (Instruct Centre FR1) for the third Instruct Workshop for Best Practice in CryoEM. Experts from leading cryoEM facilities gave presentations under the themes of sample preparation, on the fly processing/data collection strategies, and cryo-electron

⁷ <https://instruct-eric.eu/podcasts-best-practice-in-cryoem-workshop->

tomography/FIB. All talks were filmed, and will be published online as podcasts after editing is completed.

The workshop also included a breakout session, which facilitated productive discussions on the topic of software workflows and data management and storage. The participants expressed their enjoyment of the workshop, in particular the 'nice talks and exchanges'.

6. HDX training course

Instruct-ULTRA will be funding a new training course in Hydrogen/Deuterium Exchange Mass Spectrometry (HDX-MS). The training will be hosted at the Astbury Centre at the University of Leeds (Instruct Centre UK) in May 2020, coinciding with the addition of the HDX technique to the Instruct catalogue. The workshop will cover the theory and application of HDX-MS and will include a mixture of lectures, research talks, a lab practical and data analysis session. Participants will also have the opportunity to process data relating to their own samples.

7. International training courses

Although the main focus of the Instruct-ULTRA training programme is on facility managers at Instruct-ERIC European centres, the scope of the project (particularly in WP3) means that Instruct-ULTRA has an international ambition. Hosting training courses in new continents is an obvious way to build up the international structural biology community. Numerous courses have already taken place since the start of Instruct-ULTRA, and there are several courses scheduled for 2020:

Course Name	Date and Location	Speakers
The 8th Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM	27 Sep – 9 Oct 2018, Mairiporã, Brazil	Bruno P. Klaholz (P10 – CNRS), Ludo Renault (P13 – third party)
Open SESAME & Instruct-ERIC workshop on Remote X-ray Data Collection from European Synchrotrons at Instruct-Israel	14-18 May 2018, Rehovot, Israel (participants invited from Middle East countries)	Prof Joel Sussman (P11-WEIZ), Prof Rik Wierrenga (P9-OULU)
Biophysics and Structural Biology at Synchrotrons	17-24 Jan 2019, Cape Town, South Africa	Prof Ray Owens (P2-UOXF), Dr Gwyndaf Evans (P2-UOXF)
Advanced Practical Course on In-Cell NMR & Symposium on Protein Post-translational modifications by NMR	19-23 Nov 2018, Rosario, Argentina	Roberta Pierattelli (P12-CIRMMMP)
Structure Assisted Development of Novel Therapeutics	12-16 Feb 2019, Faridabad, India	Prof Joel Sussman (P11-WEIZ)
Crio-Microscopía Electrónica: La nueva revolución en Biología Estructural y su impacto en Biomedicina	16 Aug 2019, San Jose, Costa Rica	Prof Jose Maria Carazo (P8 -CSIC)
Cryo-EM X-ray Crystallography: on the Frontier of Structural Biology	26-30 Aug 2019, Buenos Aires, Argentina	Prof Alberto Podjarny (P10-CNRS), Prof Jose Maria Carazo (P8 -CSIC)
Instruct ERIC and START project: Furthering Structural Biology in Africa	24 Mar 2020, Cape Town, South Africa	Prof Dave Stuart (P2-UOXF), Dr Gwyndaf Evans (P2-UOXF)
Instruct Theoretical and Practical Course: Integrative Structural Biology in Latin America	6-9 Oct 2020, Rosario, Argentina	Prof Alberto Podjarny (P10-CNRS), Prof Lucia Banci (P12-CIRMMMP)
The 8th Brazil School for Single Particle Cryo-EM	5-17 Nov 2020, Iguazu, Brazil	TBC

Table 1: International training workshops hosted by Instruct-ULTRA partners

8. General training for centre staff

Since the role of research infrastructure management is fairly recently established, staff at UOXF have taken initiative to arrange staff exchange visits to other research infrastructures to learn from their experience.

Naomi Gray (P2-UOXF) arranged a staff exchange to CERIC-ERIC in Trieste, Italy, April 2018, where she learned about communications, industry outreach, sustainability, business planning, project management for Horizon 2020 and research infrastructure management.

Discussions are underway for Stephanie Chapman (P2-UOXF) to undertake a similar, CORBEL-funded staff exchange to shadow the communications team at BBMRI-ERIC (Graz, Austria) during Q2 of RP3.

ARIA 2.0 Launch Workshop

Launching the next version of ARIA with a hands-on workshop and building strong and stable support networks.

Date: 14 July 2018

Location: Amsterdam NKI, Netherlands

Audience: Facility & Access Managers

Agenda:

- 11:30 Sandwich lunch and welcome
- 12:00 Managing Access to Research Infrastructure
- 12:20 ARIA
 - Introduction to ARIA
 - How does ARIA 2.0 differ from the previous version?
 - Defining a common lexicon - referring to your access in common language
- 12:40 Hands-on demonstration: ARIA 2.0 how-to
 - How to manage access (remote and physical)
 - How to integrate access and machine booking
 - Messages, notifications and emails
- 13:45 Getting help with ARIA
 - ARIA guidelines (attached)
 - Who to contact and methods we use to provide help
- 14:00 Coffee
- 14:30 Q&A session
- 15:30 What else can ARIA do?
 - Surveys
 - Networks
 - Calls
- 16:00 Hands on support session
- 17:00 Meeting Close

Appendix 2: Agenda for ARIA workshop February 2018

Instruct-ULTRA / iNEXT ARIA Workshop

Introducing version 2 of ARIA with a hands-on workshop for facility managers and service operators.

Date: 2nd February 2018 10:00-17:00 CET

Location: Amsterdam NKI, Netherlands

Audience: Facility & Access Managers

10:00	Coffee/tea and welcome	
10:30	Managing Access to Research Infrastructures	Naomi Gray / Claudia Alén Amaro
	ARIA	
10:50	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to ARIA• How does ARIA 2 differ from the previous version?• Defining a common lexicon – Referring to your access in common language	Fiona Sanderson
11:10	The Access Management Pipeline with ARIA	Fiona Sanderson / Claudia Alén Amaro
11:20	Break	
11:30	Service Catalogue Changes	Darren Hart
	Hands-on demonstration: ARIA 2 How to...	
12:00	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Manage access (remote and physical)• Integrate access and machine booking• Messages, notifications and emails	Natalie Haley / Fiona Sanderson
12:45	Lunch	
13:45	Getting help with ARIA	Natalie Haley
14:00	Q&A session	Claudia Alén Amaro / Fiona Sanderson / Natalie Haley / Naomi Gray
15:00	Coffee / Tea	
	What else can ARIA do?	
15:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Calls• Surveys• Networks	Claudia Alén Amaro / Fiona Sanderson
16:00	Hands-on support session / Break out session for iNEXT reporting	
16:50	Meeting close and future developments	Claudia Alén Amaro / Fiona Sanderson

Appendix 3: Agenda for ARIA workshop February 2020

FEB
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ARIA Workshop - CORBEL
iNEXT Instruct-ERIC

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At the ARIA workshop expect to hear about what ARIA can do for you, our most recent feature releases and what's coming around the corner!

Agenda:

0900 - Introduction to ARIA (Callum Smith)

1000 - Access management and messaging demo (Fiona Sanderson)

1030 - Success Story (TBC)

1045 - *Coffee Break*

1115 - Facility management interactive demo (Marcus Povey)

1155 - Ensuring dependability of the ARIA platform (Swapna Rekala)

1205 - Building the future of ARIA – Feedback and ideas gathering (Callum Smith)

1230 - *Lunch Break*

1330 - ARIA User Group face-to-face meeting

- **Only user group members to attend**

1530 - *Meeting Closes*

Appendix 4: Quality Approaches in Instruct Centres

Author: Elodie Caremoli

Date: 3 September 2019

Introduction

We performed an assessment exercise as part of Instruct-ULTRA to establish the level of Quality Management (formal or informal) in place across the Instruct-ERIC infrastructure. The aim was to understand the current level of implementation and establish a baseline against which progress can be measured in future years.

This study was performed by Elodie Caremoli (Trainee Quality Engineer) and Auriane Denis-Meyere (CEA Quality Engineer) at the France 2 centre in Grenoble.

Description of the study

At the beginning of this work, we constructed a questionnaire on the organisation of Quality Management in the centres. This study is based on the requirements of ISO 9001:2015 for a Quality Management System (QMS).

The questionnaire comprised 19 questions in 5 sections (annex 1) :

1. Description of the service activity, from user requests to reports and results.
2. About Platform use and user approach for the service activity.
3. The general organisation of activities in the laboratories of the centres.
4. Questions related to the management commitment (leadership) in the centres in aspects of Quality.
5. Some standard quality tools to better understand Quality management in the centres.

Based upon the yes/no and text answers from the centre managers, we extracted semi-quantitative data for each centre, then combined this to generate global data for the infrastructure.

Finally, we provide some suggestions on advancing this activity at the centres.

Results

12 questionnaires were completed by the centres; 7 questionnaires filled in at the Instruct Biennial Structural Biology conference in Madrid. Four questionnaires were sent by email. One questionnaire was answered by our centre (ISBG - France 2).

The global (pan-infra) results are represented as web diagrams.

1. Service activity

The service activity is well-managed; related to the activity description, the management of instruments, the IT security and the monitoring of research and technology projects. The relationship with suppliers is the first point where we can suggest an improvement action plan.

2. User approach

This part is also well-managed. Services are correctly described at all the centres, records are well-kept. We see an improvement about the feedback implementation for non-Instruct users. We will suggest an action on this point.

3. General organisation

The centres are well-organised. Technical problems are managed efficiently and there is a good monitoring of actions. However, there is a lack of self-assessments.

4. Leadership

About the management of the centres, strategy and objectives are not often well understood by the managers. There is no SWOT approach and periodic reviews of activities are not performed at all centres. However, there is a great promotion of service activities.

Quality tools

Quality Management is under-represented.

No Quality manager in most centres. Only one centre has certifications.

The managers are not aware of national resources to help them implement quality approaches.

Despite this, the Quality meaning is excellent.

ACTION PLAN

Context	Quality approach in Instruct centres
Objectives	Improve the organisation and go ahead a certification program with the help of practical examples

Prioritisation	Objectives	Actions	Managers	Resources	2019	2020	2021	Key performance indicators
1	Organisation of the service activity	Description of service provided : List of equipments and define which are critical, type of accepted samples, result reporting format, check of documents that you need to realise on each step of the service, control recording maintenance for your equipments, description of general conditions	Core facility managers	Complete team	X			Re-assessment of the centres in 2 years (new questionnaire, diagnostic)
2	Have a feedback of all the users	Implement a satisfaction study for the non-Instruct users ; keep all email communication and keep their approval when you send the results	Core facility managers	Complete team	X			Platform user opinions are kept (formal return or significant)
3	Improvement of the assessment and the relationship with suppliers	Relationship with suppliers : - Find the selection requirements (price, localisation, products) - List of suppliers - Order monitoring - problem tracking Supplier assessment : Find the selection requirements (Order compliance, customer relationship, price, delivery time, reliability...) and about metrics, Find selection requirements for a re-assessment (frequency, type)	Core facility managers, Administrative and financial manager	Complete team		X		Assessment of all critical suppliers regarding to their performance (with metrics)
4	Have a Quality coordinator	Appoint a Quality referent : Define the Quality coordinator key skills, Describe specifications in the job description	Core facility managers	Financial resources if you need to create a position			X	Quality coordinator position
5	Do a self-assessment of your organisation	Define the method for an internal audit ; frequency, program, implementation Organise an internal audit	Core facility managers	Complete team Internal auditor			X	Internal audit performed

Instruct-ULTRA

Annex 1 Quality management questionnaire

Name :
Function :
Instruct center (facility):

INSTRUCT QUESTIONNAIRE

1: Description of your service activity

About activities in your lab or center, from user requests until reports and results.

1. Is your service activity described somewhere?

- Which documents or records do you use?

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.....
.....

- How do you take care of your samples? (ID, control, tracking, biohazard, property, preservation...)

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2. How do you manage your equipment?

- What is the maintenance, checks or calibration that you do on your equipment?

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- Do you do training sessions?
- Do you keep a list of trained users?
- Explain how do you record operations on the machines?

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3. About your relationship with your suppliers:

- Do you do a record when you have difficulties?
- Do you do assessments of your suppliers?
- Explain how do you manage your relationship with your suppliers?

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4. How do you follow and record your research and technologic development projects?

- Do you use Lab books?
- Do you do meetings?
- Do you write reports?

5. Which kind of IT Tools do you use to store and protect data from your activities?

- Do you have personal session?
- Do you use antivirus software program?
- How do you save your data?

2: User approach for your service activity

About platform use

6. How do you present to users all services that lab can offer?

- Do you have a website?
- Do you have a catalogue?
- Other;

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7. How do you do the record for user requests?

- Do you have a booking system?
- Do you use a form about analysis requests?
- Other/ comments;

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8. Have you implemented a feedback for your non-Instruct users?

- Do you do a satisfaction survey?
- Other;

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3: General organisation

About your organisation in the laboratories of the center

9. How do you manage technical problems?

- Do you have records?
- How do you communicate with users and other impacted people?

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.....

10. How do you follow your actions of your activities?

- Do you have action plans?
- Do you have records of monitoring and closure?
- Other/ comments;

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11. Do you do self-assessments of your organisation? If yes, by which mean?

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4: Leadership

About the management commitment in your lab.

12. Could you explain how your strategy and objectives are defined? (Executive committee, Science Advisory Board, frequency, number of people)

- Other;

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.....

13. Do you make a review of your activities? If yes, by which mean?

- Do you speak about metrics?
- Do you review issues?

14. Do you have a SWOT approach? (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)

- If yes, when?

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15. How do you promote your service activities?

- Do you present frequently your activities at conferences?
- Do you do papers? Or posters?
- Other;

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5: Quality tools

To know more about your knowledges in Quality management.

16. In your center/lab, do you have a person in charge of Quality as a Quality manager or a Quality coordinator?

17. Do you have national resources to help you to implement a Quality Management System?

- Do you have a budget allocation from government structure...?

18. Do you follow a certification plan?

- If yes, which one?

19. What does Quality mean to you? (Time, costs, benefits)